

A(z) – ANALITIK FUNKSIYALAR UCHUN KARLEMAN FORMULASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kompleks tekislikdagi $D \subset \mathbb{C}$ - qavariq soha va bu sohada kompakt yotuvchi $L(a; R) \subset\subset D$ lemniskatada $A(z)$ – analitik funksiyalar uchun Karleman funksiyasi analogi olingan.

Kalit soʻzlar. Kompleks tekislik, qavariq soha, lemniskata, Lebeg oʻlchovi, analitik funksiya, Karleman formulasi

Bizga kompleks tekislikdagi $D \subset \mathbb{C}$ - qavariq soha va bu sohada kompakt yotuvchi $L(a; R) \subset\subset D$ lemniskata berilgan boʻlsin. $\partial L(a; R)$ lemniskata chegarasining qismi M Lebeg oʻlchovi musbat boʻlgan toʻplam boʻlsin.

$\partial L(a; R) \setminus M$ lemniskata chegarasining qismida $\frac{1}{2\pi i \left(\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau \right)}$ (bu

yerda, $z \in L(a; R)$ – fiksirlangan) $g_{z,m}(\zeta) \in H_A^\infty(L(a; R))$ – $A(z)$ – analitik funksiya aproksimatsiyalanadigan boʻlsin. Bu funksiya $f \in H_A^1(L(a; R))$ funksiyaga ortogonal deb qaraymiz va $\partial L(a; R)$ boʻyicha integrallanuvchi deb qaraymiz. Undan tashqari,

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\partial L(a; R) \setminus M} f(\zeta) \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} - g_{z,m}(\zeta) \right) \frac{d\zeta + A d\bar{\zeta}}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Bundan quyidagi formulaga kelimiz:

$$f(z) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_M f(\zeta) \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} - g_{z,m}(\zeta) \right) \frac{d\zeta + A d\bar{\zeta}}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \quad (2)$$

formulada z ni integral belgisidan tashqaridan chiqaramiz.

Endi $A(z)$ – analitik funksiyalar uchun Karleman funksiyasi analogini quramiz.

Bunda Koshi yadrosi bilan aproksimatsiyalash yordamida olingan Karleman formulasini $A(z)$ – analitik funksiyalar uchun keltiramiz. Ikki z, ζ kompleks va musbat α o‘zgaruvchili $G(z; \zeta; \alpha)$ funksiya M to‘plamda $A(z)$ – analitik Karleman funksiyasining analogi deyiladi, agar:

$$1. G(z; \zeta; \alpha) = \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} A(\tau) d\tau} + \tilde{G}(z; \zeta; \alpha), \text{ bunda } \tilde{G} \text{ funksiya } \zeta$$

o‘zgaruvchi bo‘yicha $H_A^\infty(L(a; R))$ sinfda hosil qilingan funksiya;

$$2. \frac{1}{2\pi R} \int_{\partial L(a; R) \setminus M} |G(z; \zeta; \alpha)| |d\zeta + Ad\bar{\zeta}| \leq C(z)\alpha, \text{ bunda } C(z) \text{ ifoda } z \text{ ga}$$

bog‘liq o‘zgarmas.

(2) Karleman formulasining analogidagi yadrosini (Goluzin - Krilov metodi) $A(z)$ – analitik funksiyasi uchun Karleman funksiyasi analogini misol sifatida keltirishimiz mumkin:

$$G(z; \zeta; \alpha) = \left[\frac{\varphi(\zeta)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} A(\tau) d\tau}.$$

Umuman olganda, agar G funksiya $A(\zeta)$ – analitik Karleman funksiyasi analogi bo‘lsa, u holda $A(\zeta)$ – analitik funksiya uchun Karleman formulasi to‘g‘ri:

$$f(z) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_M f(\zeta) G(z; \zeta; \alpha) (d\zeta + Ad\bar{\zeta}) \quad (3)$$

Ko‘rinadiki, (2) va (3) formulalar ekvivalent. $A(\zeta)$ – analitik funksiya uchun M. M. Lavrentev teoremasi analogini ko‘ramiz.

Teorema-1 $L(a; R)$ lemniskata, chegarasi chekli sondagi yopiq bo‘lakli - silliq jordan chiziqlaridan tuzilgan va $M - \partial L(a; R)$ ning ochiq qism to‘plami bo‘lsin. U

holda $f \in H_A^1(L(a;R))$ funksiya uchun (2) Karleman formulasining analogi mavjud, u zanjir integral yordamida quriladi va qatorga yoyiladi.

(1) limitni $A(\zeta)$ – analitik funksiya uchun Koshi yadrosiga aproksimatsiyalanayotgan $g_{z,m}(\zeta)$ ni qator ko‘rinishda ifodalab tekis yaqinlashishga tekshiramiz. $\forall z \in L(a;R), \zeta \in \partial L(a;R)$ larda

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\psi(\zeta; z)} &= \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} = \frac{1}{(\zeta - a) - (z - a) + \int_{\gamma(a; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \\ &= \frac{1}{\psi(a; \zeta) - \psi(a; z)} = \frac{1}{(\zeta - a) + \int_{\gamma(a; z)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \frac{1}{z - a + \int_{\gamma(a; z)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} = \\ &= \frac{1}{(\zeta - a) + \int_{\gamma(a; z)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \frac{1}{\zeta - a + \int_{\gamma(a; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left(z - a + \int_{\gamma(a; z)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau \right)^k}{\left(\zeta - a + \int_{\gamma(a; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau \right)^{k+1}} \end{aligned}$$

Koshi yadrosi $L(a;R)$ lemniskatada yuqoridagidek yoyildi. Endi $g_{z,m}(\zeta)$ funksiyaning tekshiramiz: $g_{z,m}(\zeta) \in H_A^\infty(L(a;R))$ funksiyaning chekli sondagi qator ko‘rinishida tanlaymiz:

$$g_{z,m}(\zeta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{(\psi(z; a))^k}{(\psi(\zeta; a))^{k+1}} = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{\left(z - a + \int_{\gamma(a; z)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau \right)^k}{\left(\zeta - a + \int_{\gamma(a; \zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau \right)^{k+1}}$$

Endi limitga o‘tsak,

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\partial L(a;R) \setminus M} f(\zeta) \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \overline{\int_{\gamma(z;\zeta)} A(\tau) d\tau}} - g_{z,m}(\zeta) \right) \frac{d\zeta + Ad\bar{\zeta}}{\zeta - z + \overline{\int_{\gamma(z;\zeta)} A(\tau) d\tau}} =$$

$$= \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\partial L(a;R) \setminus M} f(\zeta) \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\psi(z;a))^k}{(\psi(\zeta;a))^{k+1}} - \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{(\psi(z;a))^k}{(\psi(\zeta;a))^{k+1}} \right) = 0.$$

Endi

1- teoremani isbotlaymiz:

Teoremaning isboti. Umumlashgan Runge teoremasidan kelib chiqadiki, $\partial L(a;r) \setminus M$ $A(z)$ –lemniskata chegarasining kompakt qismida kichik $\varepsilon \geq 0$ olinganda $O_A(L(a;R)_\varepsilon)$ - qavariq kompakt to‘plam hosil bo‘ladi. $K_m, m \in \mathbb{N}, K_m \subset K_{m+1}, \bigcup_m K_m = L(a;R)$ $A(z)$ –lemniskatani kompakt to‘plamlar ketma-ketligini ajrataylik,

har bir K_m kompakt $O_A(L(a;R)_\varepsilon)$ - qavariq hosil qiladi. $\frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\zeta - z + \overline{\int_{\gamma(z;\zeta)} A(\tau) d\tau} \right)$

yadro $O_A((\partial L(a;r) \setminus M) \times K_m)$ dagi har bir funksiya $O_A(L(a;r)_\varepsilon \times L(a;r)_\varepsilon)$ kompaktda tekis yaqinlashadi. Buni yuqorida $g_{z,m}(\zeta)$ funksiyaning qator ko‘rinishida ifodalab, tekis yaqinlashishni ko‘rdik. Bu yerda, $O_A(L(a;R)_\varepsilon)$ kompakt to‘plamni qavariqligidan $\partial L(a;r) \setminus M$ ni qavariqligi va $O_A(L(a;r)_\varepsilon \times L(a;r)_\varepsilon)$ dan $(\partial L(a;r) \setminus M) \times K_m$ qavariqlik kelib chiqadi. $(\partial L(a;r) \setminus M) \times K_m$ atrof bo‘yicha olingan 2 karrali Koshining integral formulasi yordamida kelib chiqadi va shuningdek, integral yig‘indining limiti integral hosil qiladi. Shuningdek, $(\partial L(a;r) \setminus M) \times K_m$ da

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \overline{\int_{\gamma(z;\zeta)} A(\tau) d\tau}} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_{m,n(m)}(\zeta; z)$$

ni qaraylik, bunda $n = n(m)$ shunday tanlandiki, qaralayotgan kompakt

$$\left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{\zeta - z + \int_{\gamma(z;\zeta)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} - f_{m,n(m)}(\zeta; z) \right|_{K_m} < \frac{1}{m}$$

o‘rinli bo‘ladi. Demak, (2) $A(z)$ – analitik funksiyalar uchun Karleman formulasi mavjud.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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